

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF COTTON FIBERS FROM VARIOUS SELECTION VARIETIES

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Abstract: This scientific article investigates the physical-mechanical and spinning-technological properties of cotton fibers from the selection varieties "Namangan 77" and "C 82/95" under laboratory conditions. According to the results, the strength, linear density, staple length, and other technological parameters of the cotton fibers were determined, and their impacts on the quality of the finished yarn were evaluated.

Keywords: cotton fiber, physical-mechanical properties, spinning-technological properties, linear density, staple length.

Introduction: Cotton fiber is one of the strategic products of Uzbekistan's economy, with its quality significantly affecting various sectors of the national economy. Particularly, the physical-mechanical and spinning-technological properties of fibers play a decisive role in producing high-quality yarns. Improving the technological properties of cotton fibers and identifying optimal selection varieties are urgent tasks today. New varieties created through selection works in our country, such as "Namangan 77" and "C 82/95," demonstrate high efficiency, opening considerable opportunities for the textile industry. This study aims to deeply analyze the physical-mechanical and spinning-technological parameters of cotton fibers from the "Namangan 77" and "C 82/95" varieties and evaluate the quality indicators of yarn produced from them.

Methods: The research was conducted using the "Sherley" small-scale laboratory spinning machine. The strength, linear density, and staple length of cotton fibers were tested according to GOST and UzDST standards. During the research, yarns with a linear density of 18.5 tex ($N_e = 32$) were produced.

Strength was determined using the formula: where R is strength (cN/tex), F is the breaking force (cN), and T is linear density (tex).

Results: Table 1. Cotton fiber properties.

Parameters	"Namangan 77"	"C 82/95"
Linear density, mtex	177	181
Staple length, mm	33.7	33.0
Strength, cN/tex	26.6	25.8

The linear density of the "Namangan 77" cotton variety was determined to be 177 mtex, which is 4 units lower than "C 82/95." Furthermore, the staple length of "Namangan 77" was found to be 33.7 mm, longer than "C 82/95." The strength indicator for "Namangan 77" was also higher (26.6 cN/tex).

Based on experimental results, the unevenness coefficient (U) of yarn breaking load was calculated using the following formula: where σ is the standard deviation, and \bar{x} is the mean value.

The calculated unevenness coefficient was 16.2%, indicating the yarn quality classified as "A."

Conclusion: The research results demonstrate that the "Namangan 77" variety exhibits optimal physical-mechanical and spinning-technological properties suitable for producing high-quality yarn. These results have significant practical implications for the local textile industry by enabling the production of superior-quality products. This research confirmed that the "Namangan 77" selection variety possesses superior technological properties, making it highly suitable for quality yarn production. These findings provide a basis for further improvements in cotton fiber deep processing technologies.

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